

Isolation of bacteria through gram staining from liver of Frog

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SUMMARY

The rising influence of human incursions in animal habitat on human illness onset and recurrence has increased interest in emerging infectious diseases of wildlife. Despite breakthroughs in treatment and prevention, bacterial infections continue to represent a substantial danger to global public health. Understanding how pathogenic microorganisms intermingle with their hosts to cause clinical illness is critical. The discovery of new virulence factors that might work as marks for vaccine and medicine progress is an important first step in this approach. A study to isolate microorganisms from frogs was proposed. Throughout the investigation, 62%, 43%, 24%, and 12% turbulence was seen, indicating that a high pathogen was present in the frog. The existence of opportunistic pathogenic microorganisms in frogs was discovered in this investigation.

Keywords: Frog, Liver, Bacteria, Pathogen

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INTRODUCTION

Anurans, sometimes known as frogs or toads, are amphibians. In many places, including Nigeria, their flesh is a well-liked as a cause of protein (Ondeko *et al.*, 2011). Frogs are raised commercially for human consumption is significant importers of frog meat (Baygar and Ozyur, 2010). Legs of frog are the major components consumed in most of these nations, and are considered a delicacy. These creatures are widely nations. High consumption rates have been observed restaurants, as well as in Turkish tourist communities (Baygar and Ozyur, 2010). Frogs/amphibians have been utilised in the manufacture of baby food. The green frog, leopard frog, and bullfrog were the most often imported for eating (Helfrich *et al.*, 2009; Onadeko *et al.*, 2011; Amuzie and Akani, 2017).

A better knowledge of the variety, origin, and significance of skin of amphibian microbiota, including the impact of habitat and host species, has emerged as a critical concern in the complex web of interactions connected to emerging illness in this animals group. The makeup and importance of bacterial communities in amphibian habitats (Loudon *et al.*, 2014) and the antibacterial properties of compounds generated by skin bacteria are two subjects that are significant (Lauer *et al.*, 2008; Lam *et al.*, 2011) Environmental changes may cause changes in the skin microbial population, decreasing its ability to act as a mechanism of inhibitory for

infections. According to the “Baas-Becking model”, the environment acts as a “selective filter”, accounting for some of the unique variance in diversity of microb (Bass-Becking *et al.*, 1934). Whereas if microbiota of skin of frogs verifies this idea, the skin bacterial community structure will be mostly determined by the environment of the amphibian skin and less by biotic links within the bacterial community. Frogs, are utilized as pets, educational and research tools, and in a number of businesses (Pasteris *et al.*, 2006). Frogs that were taken in the wild until the early twentieth century are now successfully farmed in different countries (Amborski *et al.*, 1983).

Regrettably, farming activities frequently raise the danger of sickness and death (Pasteris *et al.*, 2006). Frogs come into touch with a variety of potentially harmful microorganisms in the aquatic environment. Stressful environments, such as overcrowding or poor sanitation, allow illness to overcome weaker immunological defences (Mauel *et al.*, 2002; Austin and Austin, 2007).

The fungal infection “*Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*” causes amphibian death and is linked to population decreases and extinctions in many parts of the world (Berger *et al.*, 1998; Carey *et al.*, 2003; Lips *et al.*, 2005). This Chytridiomycete fungus is connected with keratinized tissues on amphibian skin (Carey *et al.*, 2003). Antimicrobial peptides released by several salamander and frog species can suppress the fungus (Austin, 2000; Corrento *et al.*, 2004; Rollins-Smith *et al.*, 2005; Kobolkuti *et al.*, 2013).

The rising influence of human incursions in animal habitat on human illness onset and recurrence has increased interest in emerging infectious diseases of wildlife. Despite breakthroughs in treatment and prevention, bacterial infections continue to represent a substantial danger to global public health (Sousa *et al.*, 2003). Bacterial pathogenicity can be increased by using virulence factors. Capsules, enzymes, colonisation factors (adhesions), invasions, and poisons are examples of these. Bacterial disease is caused by the complicated interactions between bacteria and the host (Wu *et al.*, 2008). A study to isolate microorganisms from frogs was proposed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

SAMPLE COLLECTION

Bull Frog was found in the area of Bagh, Azad Jammu & Kashmir. The frog was recognised using Khan's book "Amphibian and Reptiles of Pakistan" (2006).

ISOLATION OF BACTERIA

Sample Preparation

In a mortar, one gramme of frog liver and intestine was “dissected out”, combined, as well as mixed appropriately. It was moved aseptically to a sample vial containing “9 ml of 0.1%” sterile peptone water. After shaking bottle well for “10 minutes” and allowing it to stand for “20 minutes”, a “10 fold serial dilution” was performed in triplicate and viable aerobic bacterial counts were listed in “standard plate count” agar after “48 hours” of incubation at “37°C” as specified (Kolhatkar, 2004).

Preparation of Nutrient agar, and Nutrient broth and Macconkey Agar

Each dehydrated media, Nutrient agar (NA-193), Macconkey agar, and Nutrient broth (NB-1704), was mixed individually in an appropriate proportion of distilled water, heated for 1 minute with regular agitation. Autoclaving sterilised the nutritional agar (121oC for 15 minutes). Let the medium to solidify after dispensing it into the plate.

Streak plate method

Nutrient agar plats were prepared, and samples were streaked over these plats with a sterile inoculating loop and parallel over looping strokes before labelling the plate. After flaming the loop and let it to cool, spin the loop at a right angle. Overlap the previous streaks and repeat the streaking method on the plat before storing it in the incubator overnight at 30oC. Bacterial colonies were examined after incubation. The example bacterial colonies were chosen based on differences in form and size. Select colonies from each plat were marked and subcultured onto agar plates before being incubated overnight. To assess the purity of cultures, colonies were studied on agar plat.

Stock Preparation

Stack was made by combining 600 glycerol and 400 bacterial samples in an ependroff and placing it in the fridge.

Bacterial Isolation and Presumptive identification

The experiment was carried out soon following collection. Bacteria isolated from the sample sides (described above) were cultured on nutrient agar for 18 to 24 hours at 37 degrees Celsius. Each colony was subjected to biological tests. The findings were then compared to the noun properties of bacteria described in Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology (Bizzini *et al.*, 2010).

Bacterial growth on Macconkey Agar

After preparing Macconkey agar plats, the material was streaked onto them using a sterile inoculating loop with parallel over lapping strokes and the plat was labelled. Allowing the loop to cool after flameing it, I rotated it at the correct angle. Overlapped the previous streaks and repeated the striking operation on the plat before placing it in an incubator overnight at 300 degrees Celsius. After checking the bacteria in the incubator (Quinn *et al.*, 2002), it was one of the first culture medium used for cultivating and identifying intestinal microbes (Macconkey, 1905).

Examination of bacteria in tissues

Demonstration of the bacteria frog was done utilizing special staining by “gram’s staining” changes. Thin sections of the body lever from both the upstream and downstream were stand by special “gram’s staining method” for bacterial examination.

Quantitative Turbidmetric Method

A graded concentration of the chemical to be tested was introduced to a succession of test tubes containing liquid nutritional medium in this approach. This medium was

inoculated with the test organism and incubated for the appropriate amount of time. The test organism's reaction, as evidenced by the growth of turbidity, was measured by eye observation and end point, as well as the use of a photometric photometer. When the reaction of the test organism to the chemical tested is compared to the response of the test organism to a recognised standard preparation, 24%=2% (Brazilian pharmacopoeia 2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During research noted that 62%, 43%, 24%, 12% turbulence was noted, it showed that high pathogen was present in frog (Table 1). D'Silva (2015), on the other hand, observed an economically bearable death time in growth of frog of “20%” during the phase of spawning, “10%” during the tadpole phase, 35% during juvenile phases, and “10%” during the phase of fattening. Scientists believe the high rate of larval mortality was caused by gas bubble illness because we noticed huge greening of water as well as, mainly in the afternoons, increased air bubbles on the pools water surface and in the abdomens of “tadpoles” (Dökenel and Selmin, 2019). Likewise, Lutz and Avery (1999) found that tadpoles are especially vulnerable to bubble illness, which is induced by the “oxygen supersaturation” linked with afternoon “algal photosynthesis”.

The existence of opportunist pathogenic microorganisms in frogs was discovered in this investigation. This is, as far as we know, the first microbiological investigation on frogs. Further research is needed to ensure the long-term survival of the marsh frog and the safety of human and frog wellbeing.

Figure 1: Streaking of bacterial pathogen on agar plate with dilution.

Figure 2. Gram staining of bacterial colony.

Table 1: Quantification of bacteria from frog liver through Turbidimetric Method

Pathogen	Quantification (turbulence)
Frog liver bacteria(1)	62%
Frog liver bacteria(2)	43%
Frog liver bacteria(3)	24%
Frog liver bacteria(4)	12%

Note: Quantification of Turbidimetric Method control value =0.024

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